

An Empirical Analysis on the Causal Relationship between Currency Intervention and the Asymmetry of Volatility in Foreign Exchange Markets

Abstract

This dissertation sets out to identify whether intervention by monetary authorities in currency markets has a causal effect on Volatility Asymmetry (VA). Specifically, the study hypothesises that both the asymmetry in frequency and in volatility impact of intervention work in conjunction to produce the overall VA effect observed. This work expands upon existing literature by exploring the potential intervention channels through which VA might arise, and by examining a broader range of currency pairs. To this end, three variations of the Threshold GARCH model were utilised: a baseline model, which aimed to identify the presence of VA, and two adjusted models, which sought to capture the impact of intervention on conditional variances. The econometric framework captures VA in three out of the four models, and identified that central bank intervention has a statistically significant impact in causing VA. Moreover, the model found that the impact of purchases versus sales exhibits asymmetry in its effect on conditional variances. The findings of this analysis provides convincing evidence for the hypothesis; both intervention frequency and impact must be considered to reconcile the three model specifications and to identify the overall VA effect.

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Introduction

Volatility asymmetry (VA) is the observed phenomenon that conditional variances are negatively correlated with asset returns, that is, negative shocks tend to create greater volatility responses relative to positive shocks. Although VA has been extensively observed and researched in equity markets, its presence in foreign exchange markets has only recently been recognized.

Understanding exchange rate dynamics at the second moment is important to both investors and policymakers. The foreign exchange market represents the largest and most liquid financial market in the world (Scott, 2022), and its behaviours influence all non-domestic, currency-denominated assets. Thus, for investors, a more nuanced understanding of volatility allows for more accurate ex-ante modelling of other asset classes, such as foreign equities and bonds, and allows for more rigorous approaches to risk management. Indeed, Engle (2004) concluded that by including volatility asymmetry in Value at Risk calculations, the statistic is “substantially larger than the value assuming constant volatility”, thus its omission would mean investors are undervaluing the downside risk they face.

Considerations of VA also allow for a more cognizant reaction of investors to exogenous shocks with respect to their risk tolerances, as they may be able to forecast the post-shock currency impact more accurately. This can be highlighted by repurposing the work of Ding and Granger (1996). They found that the predictive power of their out-of-sample asset price forecasting was highly dependent on preciseness of volatility forecasts. By capturing the effects of volatility more accurately through VA, exchange rate forecasting may be even more reliable.

VA is also an important consideration within hedging strategies. Consider the Heston Model, which captures the stochastic volatility processes of an underlying asset, in this case the exchange rate, in order to price an option. Incorporating volatility asymmetry means that the model can account for the unequal magnitude of volatility responses, leading to more accurate pricing of currency derivatives, thus helping investors make better informed decisions regarding currency hedging. Notably, Melino and Turnbull (1990) found that by better capturing the stochastic behaviour of exchange rate volatility “results in more accurate predictions of observed option prices”.

For policy makers, interventions may be counter-productive if their aim is to temper erratic currency movements. As discussed below, previous literature has argued that, due to inaccurate signalling of future monetary policy and its impacts on macroeconomic variables, specific central bank interventions may induce a greater degree of volatility. This means VA should be

considered when central banks deliberate the method of intervention, as sterilised versus non-sterilised, currency purchases versus sales, and disclosed versus undisclosed intervention may have differing impacts on the volatility response. This is because the degree of impact on macroeconomic factors and the strength of signalling will differ depending on the method of implementation.

The primary objective of this dissertation is to investigate whether a central bank's intervention in the foreign exchange market, through currency purchases and sales, is contributing to the creation of VA in currency markets. Additionally, this dissertation aims to address a research gap by investigating the potential channels through which VA might arise, as well as by examining VA for a broader group of exchange rates which have not yet been extensively explored in the existing literature. More specifically, the selected currencies for this analysis are the Australian Dollar (AUD), Japanese Yen (JPY), Mexican Peso (MXN) and Turkish Lira (TRY), all paired against the US dollar. To this end, the econometric framework employed in this study utilises the Threshold GARCH model proposed by Zakoian (1994), given its ability to capture asymmetric effects on conditional variances. This dissertation builds on Zakoian's methodology by incorporating additional variables to capture the effects of central bank intervention. Furthermore, updated datasets are used to evaluate the persistence of VA for currencies that have been previously identified to exhibit this effect.

The findings of this research are largely consistent with existing literature, revealing that most currencies exhibit VA, though the direction may vary across currency pairs. Additionally, the study demonstrates that central bank intervention plays a statistically significant role in the cause of volatility asymmetry across three out of the four currencies considered.

The structure of the dissertation is as follows. Section 1 provides an overview of the historic literature relating to volatility asymmetry causality/behaviour and addresses their limitations and drawbacks whilst also comparing relevant econometric models. Section 2 discusses the economic theory underlying the model by examining central bank intervention transmission mechanisms and how this relates to volatility asymmetry, as well as defining the hypothesis of the dissertation in more detail. Section 3 considers the specification and significance of the Threshold GARCH model. Section 4 looks into the behaviour, structure and sources of the data used within the model and how it may influence model results. Section 5 then presents the model results and interprets them in light of the economic theory discussed in section 2, as well as in comparison with previous literature. Finally, section 6 summarises the findings and discusses their policy implications.

Literature Review

The phenomenon of volatility asymmetry was first documented by Black (1976), who observed the tendency for negative shocks to cause greater volatility than positive shocks in US equity markets. Its existence has since been widely associated with leveraging effects (Black, 1976) and feedback loops (Pindyck, 1984) for equities. However, it is broadly accepted that neither effect plays a significant role in the inception of volatility asymmetry in foreign exchange markets. The application of volatility asymmetry research to foreign exchange markets has only gained momentum in recent years, due to the advent of more advanced volatility models and proliferated availability of higher-frequency FX data. Early research, such as that of Bollerslev et al. (1992), concluded that volatility asymmetry likely does not exist in currency markets. He suggested “whereas stock returns have been found to exhibit some degree of asymmetry in their conditional variances, the two-sided nature of the foreign exchange market makes such asymmetries less likely.” However, this conclusion was based on a linear GARCH(p,q) model which lacked an asymmetric specification, which could have led to a potential misspecification issue, alongside the now outdated conclusion.

More recent literature suggests that the existence of VA in currency markets is idiosyncratic to the currency pair. Whilst a systematic review of exchange rate VA is not present in the literature, evidence for its existence has been found non-exhaustively with the Malaysian Ringgit (Tse, 1997), Australian Dollar (McKenzie, 2002) and Mexican Peso (Adler, 2003), all versus the dollar. All three papers use variations of the GARCH model in order to capture asymmetric effects: APARCH, TGARCH and GARCH-M models, respectively. Each model captures standard ARCH and GARCH effects, but notably also include an additional parameter on the variance estimator to capture regime shifts that drive asymmetric behaviours. However, whilst the above studies consider decades-long data series, they do not capture contemporary foreign exchange dynamics. Moreover, Tse’s and Adler’s research lack economic reasoning for the existence of VA, and whilst McKenzie argues that central bank intervention is the cause of VA, the paper’s findings fall short in explaining the intricate mechanisms by which this might occur. McKenzie provides the theoretical and econometric framework which this dissertation aims to build upon by using updated datasets, evaluating other currency pairs and by looking more in depth at the intervention channels that may cause VA.

Early work comparing variations of GARCH models includes Pagan and Schwert (1990) who found that EGARCH models have greater explanatory power over standard GARCH models due to its considerations of the “asymmetric relation between volatility and past returns” when explaining volatility in equity markets. Kandora and Hamdi (2016) in their comparison of various volatility models found that both symmetric and asymmetric GARCH models better fit

currency dynamics when returns are non-normally distributed (versus a Gaussian distribution). When considered through the lens of Coppes' (1995) findings that daily returns are leptokurtic (non-normal) and that monthly returns are more normal, then asymmetric GARCH models should see greater explanatory power when fitted against daily or even intra-day data. This provides clarity to Arachchi's (2018) comparison of Asymmetric and Symmetric GARCH models among the top five most stable currencies against the Sri Lankan Rupee, finding that different asymmetric models provided greater explanatory power depending on the different currency pairs considered, though these consistently outperformed symmetric GARCH models.

Andersen et al. (2003) modelled realized volatilities of exchange rates as a fractionally integrated process to capture long-memory volatility, finding evidence that exogenous shocks have persistent effects on the volatility across long time horizons for specific currency pairs. Wang (2009) finds evidence supporting this view. He uses a Heterogeneous Autoregressive Realized Volatility (HAR-V) model to "adequately account for the long-memory autocorrelations observed in realized volatility series" for the AUD, JPY, GBP, and EUR. He finds evidence of VA for the former three but not for EUR, supporting the view that the VA existence is idiosyncratic to the currency pair and not a universal phenomenon. This research is also significant because it postulates that currency base-effects work in tandem with currency intervention to drive asymmetric behaviours – pointing to multiple causes of VA. However, the use of this more advanced econometric model requires a higher frequency of data (here, intra-day trading data is used) and thus greater computational power. Furthermore, Wang only considers G10 currency pairs which are the most heavily traded currencies and are thus the most liquid. This is significant, as exogenous shocks may have a tempered volatility impact on the exchange rate relative to that of a less liquid currency pair, as the shock is more rapidly absorbed by the market. The author also fails to identify differentials in currency/economy fundamentals that might drive why some currencies experience VA whilst others do not.

In that light, Cho (2022) provides some insight into VA behaviours across different classes of currencies. They find that safe haven currencies (US dollar, Swiss franc, Japanese yen) have a diametrically opposing relationship to volatility compared to risk-on currencies; it is the appreciation of such currencies that lead to higher relative future volatility, as opposed to depreciation. Notably, this effect is exacerbated during times of higher pre-existing volatility, which they argue is due to the tendency for increased safe-haven exposure during volatile trading periods which drives safe-haven valuations higher. They also find that future volatility is more strongly associated with past appreciations compared to past depreciations, thus strong safe-haven appreciation may lead to greater currency volatility. However, they do not explain why appreciation of safe havens tend to lead to greater future volatility, thus misses a crucial

link for the inverted VA relationship of safe haven currencies. Her findings also go against that of Baur and Dimpfl (2018) who found a lack of evidence of asymmetric exchange rate volatility responses, except during phases of pre-heightened volatility.

Bevilacqua (2018) looks at volatility spill-over effects between Developed and Developing European countries across various asset classes using the Diebold-Yilmaz spillover index, finding the Brexit vote to be the biggest contributor to volatility spillovers in currency markets. Within the theoretical framework, Bevilacqua accounts for the effects of VA on volatility spillovers using a decomposed realized volatility measure, finding that “connectedness level” explained a significant portion of volatility asymmetry, evidence of VA spillover effects between different economies. This introduced a new perspective of VA, as prior literature focused on isolated effects. The findings were supported by Rai and Kumar (2020) who used EGARCH models to find evidence of volatility asymmetry transmission between BRIC countries and their periphery economies. Notably though, both studies fall short in providing an argument for the initial origin of VA. Furthermore, the former paper focuses on CEE economies whilst the latter considers BRIC economies, both of which are undergoing significant financial market deregulation and capital movement liberalisation. Thus, greater financial market integration will be observed for the considered economies, likely increasing the effects of VA spillover compared to other developing economies where these dynamics are less prevalent. This means the observations may not be applicable for all developing economies, especially those less integrated into the global economy.

Krugman (1991) and Flood (1991) found that intervention can have a stabilising effect on the exchange rate within specific bands, if the central bank intervention policy is known and credible. Connolly and Taylor (1994), using EGARCH models, finds contrary evidence for the Japanese yen, stating that Bank of Japan intervention consistently had a causal effect on higher volatility between 1977 and 1979. Bonser-Neal (1996) finds support for this, noting “central bank intervention is generally associated with a positive change in ex-ante exchange rate volatility”. She identifies the importance of whether intervention was credible and expected by market participants, providing an important link to McKenzie’s argument for how central bank intervention causes greater volatility responses. However, she uses currency option prices as a proxy for ex-ante volatility which relies upon options markets being efficient and the option pricing model being correct. There also exists a salient risk of simultaneity bias; if a central bank intervenes during the same time as volatility regime shifts e.g. following economic surprise, an element of bidirectional causality might arise.

Calvo and Reinhart (2002) provides insight into why central bank intervention may cause greater volatility. They point to a “fear of floating” hypothesis whereby intervention may

influence other macroeconomic variables such as inflation and interest rates, which markets may interpret as bad news. Maya and Gomez (2008) found strong evidence of this hypothesis for Brazil and Peru, noting that “only countries with ‘fear of floating’ show asymmetric responses to volatility shocks”, and that currencies that have not faced central bank intervention expect shocks to be “absorbed through the exchange rate”.

Conversely, Beattie (1999) found that discretionary currency intervention had a stabilising effect on the USDCAD exchange rate from 1995 to 1997 through the use of a well-communicated non-intervention bands whilst stating that expected intervention had no direct impact on exchange rate volatility. He posits two channels through which central bank intervention can temper exchange rate volatility. First is the liquidity approach, where the provision of liquidity by central banks reduces the risk of market making, which in turn encourages dealers to provide further liquidity creating more “orderly” adjustments in the exchange rate. Second is the signalling channel which assumes that central banks have insider information on the direction of future monetary policy which would reduce the volatility of exchange rates if the message conveyed by the central bank is one of volatility reduction. However, Dominguez (1993) found that between 1977-93, only 50% of intervention signals from G3 central banks were consistent with the observed direction of future monetary policy, suggesting that the latter channel may be limited in its consistency. Furthermore, Beattie argues that FX markets are efficient and react rapidly to new information thus longer-term volatility impacts of central bank intervention is omitted here. This clashes against Wang’s (2009) methodology, which purposefully attempted to capture longer-term volatility impacts of intervention.

Background – Theoretical Framework

Floating exchange rates and intervention

A floating exchange rate is a regime where the value of a currency versus another is determined by the market forces of supply and demand. Despite this, central banks of floating currencies often intervene in foreign exchange markets to prevent excessive volatility or significant exchange rate pressures that could undermine macroeconomic stability. This was seen with the Swiss franc; despite being priced by market determination, the SNB implemented significant currency intervention following the 2008 financial crisis, in order to prevent sustained CHF appreciation. The most common method of intervention is through the purchase and sale of foreign currency in exchange for domestic currency. This exchange affects the relative supply and demand for each currency, thus driving the exchange rate impact. Central banks can also intervene through monetary policy, such as changing interest rates or implementing quantitative easing measures or through indirect methods, such as capital controls. In this dissertation, only the impact of foreign currency purchases/sales will be considered.

Central bank intervention transmission mechanisms

Understanding the mechanisms of how central bank intervention affects the exchange rate is essential for understanding the potential causes of volatility asymmetry. This is because it is likely through these channels that intervention causes asymmetric behaviours from market participants.

An important distinction made in the literature is the difference between sterilized and non-sterilised central bank intervention regimes. Non-sterilised intervention involves central bank intervention which alters the monetary base without any subsequent round of intervention to offset this effect – the impact on the money supply persists. Meanwhile, sterilised intervention has no net effect on the monetary base as the central bank implements supplementary policy that returns the money supply back to its pre-intervention level.

Non-sterilized intervention by central banks can impact the exchange rate through two primary channels, both of which feed through money supply manipulation. The central bank funds the purchases of foreign currency through the sale of domestic currency – an equivalent exchange occurs. On the central bank's balance sheet, this exchange represents an increase in both domestic currency liabilities and foreign currency assets. This increased balance sheet can then affect the money supply; any funding method that injects additional liquidity to the banking system, such as through new currency issuance or increasing commercial bank reserves, will increase the money supply. This leads to a higher circulation and supply of the domestic currency in the foreign exchange market, as consumers and businesses use the excess money to

purchase foreign goods, services and securities. This creates a relative abundance of domestic currency compared to foreign currency, applying depreciative pressure on the domestic exchange rate.

Non-sterilised intervention may also trigger the monetary channel. The increase in the money supply results in a decrease in short-term interest rates through reduced competition in money markets. This leads to a depreciation in the exchange rate due to suppressed capital inflows and lower demand for domestic currency as the potential for capital returns is reduced.

Sterilisation can then be induced by a subsequent Open Market Operation, which partially or fully offsets the monetary impact of the initial intervention. In the above example, the higher money supply can be offset by an open-market sale of domestic assets of equal size to the initial intervention, which reduces the central bank's assets and liabilities, as well as the money base, back to their pre-intervention level. Since there is no net impact on the monetary base, neither money-supply related effect is applicable for sterilized intervention, thus other intervention channels must be considered.

For example, the portfolio-balance channel suggests that the relative attractiveness of domestic versus foreign assets is altered by sterilized intervention. To put this into context, the purchase of foreign currency through sterilized intervention reduces the supply of domestic bonds in the market, causing their price to increase and their yield to decrease. As a result, investors seeking to balance exchange rate risk and expected rate of return may find domestic bonds less attractive and alter their portfolio compositions accordingly. This reduces foreign investors' holdings of domestic bonds, assuming that some degree of substitutability between domestic and foreign bonds exists. This then reduces the demand for the domestic currency, causing the depreciation.

However, evidence for the portfolio balance channel is mixed. Fatum (2015) suggests that at the zero lower bound, the portfolio-balance channel becomes the most prominent policy transmission mechanism, particularly in the case of unannounced intervention. Meanwhile, Edison (1982) provides convincing evidence that in most cases, the portfolio-balance channel falls short in a multitude of respects: the lack of substitutability across asset classes, simultaneity bias arising in the asset demand function, as well as specific examples of limited exchange rate impacts e.g. US Dollar (Thornton, 2012).

Sterilized intervention can also influence the exchange rate through the signalling channel. The theoretical foundation of this channel is predicated on the assumption that central banks have "insider information" over the direction of future monetary and fiscal policy, and that the intervention signals this to market participants. This in turn causes market participants to alter their exchange rate expectations, which can affect the spot rate as the modified expectations

also affects the expected return of foreign bonds. Therefore, under uncovered interest rate parity, the exchange rate must adjust by the same amount as the expected future exchange rate in order to re-establish parity across domestic interest rates and the expected return on bonds. Mussa (1981) argues that intervention is more credible than central bank's simply announcing exchange rate and monetary policy expectations, because the monetary authority stakes their capital in support of those policies. Notably, the signalling effect occurs regardless of whether the intervention is sterilised.

The effects of signalling are more widely accepted. Humpage (1989) and Dominguez (1990) found, through the comparisons of announced and unannounced interventions, central bank intervention had a statistically significant impact on the exchange rate through the signalling channel. However, at the zero lower bound the signalling effect has been found to be less potent (Fatum, 2015), given that available policy options are restricted, thus any intervention provides limited additional information for market participants.

Notably, it is uncommon for a central bank to take a purely sterilised or purely non-sterilised approach to intervention; typically a combination of both is utilised. However, one example of a purely sterilised intervention regime is seen with Mexico, which sterilises its intervention in order to meet the daily liquidity requirements in the money market.

Sterilized and Non-sterilized Intervention comparison – case study

The Swiss National Bank (SNB) provides an interesting case study for the comparison of impacts between sterilized versus non-sterilized intervention. The SNB faced significant upward pressure on the Swiss franc against the euro following the 2008 Global Financial Crisis stemming from significant safe-haven inflows. The SNB responded with two rounds of non-sterilized and one round of sterilized intervention to prevent further economic turmoil.

Both rounds of non-sterilized intervention induced significant reaction in the monetary base – as the theory suggests. The first round of intervention in March 2009 saw aggressive euro purchases that caused the CHF to depreciate 4.05% in 3 days. The Bank's balance sheet grew by CHF9.4bn throughout March, causing the money supply to grow 4.83% which maintained the CHF level around 1:1.5 against the euro for the rest of the year. A similar narrative occurred following August 2011, when the SNB announced it would buy foreign currency in unlimited quantities to maintain a 1.20 per euro floor, which immediately brought the franc to its target range.

The SNB also experienced a period of sterilization, where the automatic roll-off of foreign exchange swaps contracted the Swiss monetary base by 30% in the latter half of 2010. This contraction was not offset by any other monetary policy actions, effectively sterilizing the Swiss

intervention. Despite significant growth in the foreign exchange reserves of CHF138bn (Humpage, 2013) (implying substantial intervention), the Swiss franc saw sustained depreciation throughout 2010, reaching an all-time low against the euro before the end of the year. In line with the literature, sterilised intervention had limited impacts on the exchange rate.

Figure 1 – Swiss sterilized and non-sterilized intervention (SNB, 2023)

Volatility Asymmetry Causality

Within equity markets, the existence of VA is widely associated with leveraging effects (Black (1976), Christie (1982), Nelson (1991)) and feedback loops (Pindyck (1984), Campbell & Hentschel (1992)). The argument for leveraging effects is that a negative shock decreases the stock price, which increases the debt-to-equity ratio. This raises the relative financial risk that investors face and sours the stock's outlook, causing a downward revaluation of equity prices. This means that investors demand a higher risk-premium to invest in the company, reinforcing the prior shock as well as the risk associated with the stock, and when risk increases, so too does the volatility. Conversely, a positive shock causes a decrease in corporate leverage, tempering the volatility response from the shock, leading to a reduced volatility reaction relative to the negative shock.

Feedback loops are explained by volatility persistence, whereby negative shocks lead to increases in both current and future volatility. If the shock is negative i.e. stock prices decrease, volatility will be exacerbated and will cause further spillover effects in future volatility, whereas a positive shock will partially ease markets and temper the volatility feedback effect.

However, feedback loops and leveraging effects provide unconvincing arguments for the cause of VA in currency markets. Consider the leverage effect; currency fluctuations do not materially affect the value of an economy's debt-to-GDP ratio (Wahyuni, 2019) to the extent that investors will adjust their response functions. This is especially true given that debt-to-GDP ratios rarely exceed 5%, whereas debt-to-equity ratios for stocks often reach far higher strata and face higher elasticities. Likewise, feedback loops provide a limited explanation, given the bi-lateral nature of currencies. Positive and negative shocks are theoretically indistinguishable from each other, as positive returns for one currency are necessarily negative returns for the other. Therefore, investors either side of the currency pair should offset one another.

The hypothesis for this dissertation is that central bank intervention provides a cogent explanation for the existence of VA in currency markets. Intervention causes a mechanical alteration of relative currency demand and supply, which creates dissension over the direction of interest rate differentials, inflation expectations and other key macroeconomic currency return-drivers. The signalling channel may also drive VA, especially if central bank communicate is considered to be uncredible or inconsistent, as any policy implications implied by the central bank may be disingenuous. Both of these effects distort markets signals and creates heterogeneous exchange rate expectations which Macdonald and Marsh (1996) found in turn drives higher trading volumes and exchange rate volatility as conflicting buy/sell dynamics cause exchange rates to whiplash. Ultimately, the hypothesis relies on the assumption

that investors act largely in accordance with expectations over ex-ante exchange rate characteristics.

The asymmetric patterns of volatility observed are partially created through the asymmetric tendencies of central banks. In general, a central bank is more likely to intervene during depreciation periods and more likely to take a laissez-faire approach during appreciation periods. This is because significant currency depreciation is often associated with longer-term and significant changes in the macroeconomic outlook, and without central bank intervention, a weaker currency may cause further economic turmoil. Conversely, during periods of significant appreciation, the central bank may take the opportunity to rebuild their foreign exchange reserves due to often limited downside risks associated with a temporarily stronger currency.

The asymmetric implementation of intervention is evident across most central banks. Lahura (2013) notes that the Central Reserve Bank of Peru views “depreciations and appreciations as having asymmetric implications”, stemming from differing motives for purchasing and selling foreign currency – the CRBP’s primary intervention method has been purchasing foreign currency to stifle significant capital inflows. Similar trends have been documented for the Bank of Japan and Reserve Bank of India. This asymmetry in implementation can also provide an explanation for a unique behaviour in volatility asymmetry – the direction of asymmetry alters depending on whether or not the currency is a safe-haven (Cho, 2022). This behaviour may be due to differing central bank response functions and mandates resultant of distinct economic challenges and objectives, causing the central bank to intervene in different situations.

Notably, the asymmetry of the volatility impact that foreign currency purchases versus sales have may also drive VA. This may be due to additional information the intervention signals to market participants. When a central bank implements a foreign currency sale, it might suggest that a negative shock has induced wider economic turmoil, which a foreign currency purchase does not imply. Therefore, the combined impact of asymmetry of implementation and of impact lead to the overall asymmetric volatility effect observed.

Katusiime and Agbola (2018) provides some supporting evidence for the view that central bank intervention may cause VA. They find that inflation targeting is capable of reducing temporary exchange rate volatility, whilst an increase in interest rate differentials have the opposite effect. Credible inflation targeting helps anchor and lower inflation expectations among investors, such that even after central bank intervention, inflation expectations, and therefore exchange rate expectations, may not deviate significantly among market participants.

For Interest Rate Differentials (IRDs), Goyal and Arora (2012) found that higher IRDs had two opposing effects that likewise causes heterogeneous response functions. Whist higher IRDs

represents greater arbitrage opportunity through short-term carry trades, they also tend to reduce the growth outlook and thus capital inflows, depreciating the exchange rate. Therefore, the uncertainty that central bank intervention causes over interest rate differentials causes even greater uncertainty over the direction of the exchange rate.

The comparison of sterilized and non-sterilized intervention can also provide a proxy for the comparative relevance of the signalling channel versus money supply channel on the cause of volatility asymmetry. If VA is observed even when sterilized intervention is implemented, this would represent strong evidence that the signalling effect is an important factor in causing VA, since there is limited direct exchange rate impact in sterilized intervention.

Model – Econometric Framework

Model Outline

The econometric framework of this dissertation is based on the work of McKenzie (2002). Stata is used to run the regression, due to the availability of a pre-built Threshold GARCH package (see Appendix 1 for details). Currency returns are estimated using an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model with the form:

$$R_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D_{0,t} + \alpha_2 R_{t-1} + \epsilon_t; \epsilon_t \sim N(0, h_t)$$

R_t represents exchange rate returns, calculated as the log difference in the spot exchange rate. Returns are considered from a domestic currency base i.e. a positive R_t value implies the domestic currency has appreciated and the USD has depreciated. D_0 represents an ordered categorical variable taking the value of unity during net purchases of foreign currency, negative unity during net sales, and zero when no intervention is made. An ARDL regression is an appropriate specification for the mean equation, since the addition of the lagged exchange rate return variable helps to capture the persistence of currency returns (e.g. through momentum effects and investor sentiment), whilst also considering the effect of government intervention.

The conditional variances of the errors are estimated via the Threshold GARCH model proposed by Zakoian (1994). Conditional variances are used as a proxy for return volatility given that they capture a significant portion of the variation in an asset's return. Three variations of the Threshold GARCH model are considered: one baseline and two adjusted models. The baseline model takes the form:

$$h_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \delta_1 h_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{1,t-1}$$

The aim of the baseline model is to determine whether VA effects are present for the specific currency pair. In this specification, the threshold term (given by $\gamma_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{1,t-1}$) is “triggered” for values of the error term greater than zero ($\epsilon_t > 0$) and is “de-triggered” for values of $\epsilon_t \leq 0$. This dynamism is caused by the dummy variable $D_{1,t-1}$. The threshold term captures the impact of an exogenous shock on the conditional variance, thus capturing the different volatility responses from differing shock types: the asymmetry of volatility. Mechanically, when the threshold term is triggered, the composite impact of ϵ_{t-1}^2 on the conditional variance becomes $(\beta_1 + \gamma_1)$, as opposed to just β_1 when the threshold term is de-triggered.

An additional term is added in the adjusted models in order to capture the impact of central bank intervention on conditional variances. The adjusted model takes the form:

$$h_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \delta_1 h_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{1,t-1} + \gamma_j \epsilon_{t-1} D_{j,t-1}$$

The added $\gamma_j \epsilon_{t-1} D_{j,t-1}$ term takes two distinct possible forms. In one form, the dummy variable takes the value of unity when a net sale is made and 0 otherwise. This case is denoted by $j = 2$. In the other form of the model, the dummy takes the value of unity when a net purchase is made and 0 otherwise. This case is denoted by $j = 3$.

This means that for each currency, there are three models that are considered. The “Baseline” model attempts to capture whether asymmetric volatility exists for each currency pair. The “Sales Dummy” model attempts to capture the impacts of foreign currency sales on VA, whilst the “Purchase Dummy” model attempts to capture the impacts of foreign currency purchases. Having these three models then allows a comparison that can provide evidence for several key aspects of the hypothesised relationship between intervention and VA: the relative impacts of purchase versus sales, the importance of intervention frequency and the conditions for inverted VA direction.

Data – nature and structure

Data Access and Availability

Given that only a few monetary agencies publish their foreign exchange intervention data, the breadth of this analysis is restricted by the availability of appropriate data. This problem is exacerbated by the importance of analysing higher-frequency data (e.g. intraday or daily) when attempting to capture empirical regularities in foreign exchange phenomena. Since FX markets are the most liquid in the world, market participants tend to be highly reactive to any external stimulus, meaning lower-frequency data (e.g. monthly or quarterly) may obscure important statistical and behavioural tendencies. Furthermore, GARCH-type models also see greater explanatory power when fitted using higher-frequency data, as discussed previously. And whilst using intra-day data would enable the use of more advanced/insightful econometric techniques, there would be significant financial cost associated with its use.

One potential alternative includes using a proxy to estimate the level of intervention. One such example involves using the day-on-day changes in the SNB's sight deposits as a proxy for Swiss FX intervention, given that sight deposits change in tandem with foreign currency holdings. However, the SNB (2023) notes that there are other significant reasons why sight deposits would change e.g. changes in liquidity-absorbing repo transactions. Therefore, its inclusion as a variable in the regression would mean capturing unrelated effects stemming from other monetary policy actions.

The IMF (2021) provides a more comprehensive proxy for central bank intervention, which comprises of changes in foreign exchange reserves, known intervention data as well as a range of central bank operations, which they suggest provides a “more accurate measure than coarser measures traditionally used”. This would represent an important data set in this analysis as it would enable the analysis of over 40 currency pairs. However data frequency is monthly and quarterly, which means the specific timing of intervention would be obscured, which is arguably more important than the specific size of intervention, given that the hypothesis of this dissertation argues that a combination of the signalling function and alteration of market forces that creates volatility asymmetry – both of which are highly time sensitive.

Ultimately, utilising data from official sources is the only way to guarantee reliability, accessibility, and consistency throughout time. This left four currency pairs where daily intervention data was available from official government or central bank websites: JPY, AUD, MXN, and TRY. This represents a notable spread, given the range of economic development level, safe-haven versus risk-on and differing levels of central bank credibility. Figure 2 below summarises the data observations:

Figure 2 – summary of central bank intervention data

Currency	Net Foreign Purchase	Net Foreign Sale	Total
AUD (AUD millions)	16016.00	28698.50	44714.50
JPY (USD millions)	809033.00	77176.00	886209.00
TRY (USD millions)	25534.00	15951.00	41485.00
MXN (USD millions)	0.00	59449.00	59449.00

Spot data characteristics

These currencies will be compared using a USD base; there are several reasons for this. Firstly, comparing all currencies against the same base helps eliminate biases that might arise from comparing against different currencies, i.e. currency-specific factors. This ultimately aids in making the analysis less complicated. Secondly, the US dollar is the global reserve currency, meaning it forms the largest proportion of currency held at central bank foreign exchange reserves. In fact, this is true for all of the considered currencies, with the USD making up 58.3%, 63.6%, 81.1% and 57.3% of the reserves of JPY, AUD, MXN, and TRY, respectively¹. This means each central bank is more likely to intervene in markets using the USD. Indeed, for the aforementioned currencies, the purchase and sale of USD is the most common form of central bank intervention. This means that by comparing these currencies versus a dollar-base, both supply and demand dynamics following intervention will be more holistically captured.

Figures 3-6 presents combined time-series plots of central bank net purchases/sale of foreign currency versus the daily dollar-base spot average for the four currencies of interest. Note that because the exchange rate is denoted with a dollar base, domestic purchases of foreign currency will lead to domestic currency depreciation, meaning the time-series line will increase.

¹ Sources: Ministry of Finance Japan (2023), Reserve Bank of Australia (2023), Banco de Mexico (2023), Central Bank of the Republic of Turkey (2023)

Figure 3-6 – time-series progressions of exchange rates and central bank interventions

Intervention data characteristics

Figure 7 shows several statistics regarding the distribution of the intervention data. The Jarque-Bera statistic denotes whether or not the sample have the skewness and kurtosis matching that of a normal distribution. It is calculated by:

$$JB = \frac{n}{6} \left(S^2 + \frac{(K - 3)^2}{4} \right)$$

Where n denotes number of observations, S is the sample skewness and K is the sample kurtosis. Evidently, across all the currencies considered, the observed distribution is highly non-

normal. This matches theoretical expectations; intervention represents discrete, infrequent, and idiosyncratic episodes thus should not be expected to follow a normal distribution.

Figure 7 – table to show the non-normality of central bank intervention

Currency	Jarque-Bera Statistic	Skew	Kurtosis
AUD	65773440.57	-16.92	425.80
JPY	1240546997.43	32.37	1902.64
TRY	103304284.25	13.03	682.75
MXN	1598558.11	-9.11	102.41

The high kurtosis statistic observed across all currencies shows the distribution is heavy tailed. Skewness is a measure of the level of asymmetry of a probability distribution about its mean. Notably, between the currencies, there is significant variation in the direction of skewness, with JPY and TRY facing positive skews whilst for AUD and MXN face negative skews. This indicates that the former two have a disproportionate bias towards net foreign exchange purchases, with the opposite being true for the latter two. This is confirmed by Figure 8.

Figure 8 – volume of Net Foreign Purchases and Sales

Currency	Net Foreign Purchase	Net Foreign Sale	Total
AUD (AUD millions)	16016.00	28698.50	44714.50
JPY (USD millions)	809033.00	77176.00	886209.00
TRY (USD millions)	25534.00	15951.00	41485.00
MXN (USD millions)	0.00	59449.00	59449.00

It is probable that this asymmetry in implementation is an outcome of differing central bank response functions and macroeconomic fundamentals. Consider Japan, with persistent deflation and a safe-haven status. During high uncertainty/turbulence periods, sustained yen appreciation can add additional difficulty to bringing inflation up to the BoJ’s 2% target as domestic currency strength leads to relatively cheaper imports, including intermediate goods, which can lead to imported disinflation or deflation. Contrarily, Australia has historically been dependent on

commodity exports such as metal ore and fossil fuels which accounts for 12% of nominal GDP (RBA, 2023), thus AUD appreciation could provide tailwinds for the antipodean economy, given the inelasticity of essential commodities.

Model Results

Mean estimation characteristics

A notable aspect of the mean estimation results is that the ordered categorical variable D_0 is statistically significant at the $\alpha = 1\%$ significance level for all currency pairs except for USDMXN (see figure 9). This coincides with the signs of the α_1 coefficients; all are negative other than for MXN. When a central bank purchases foreign currency, D_0 takes the value of positive unity, which in turn increases the supply of the domestic currency, causing the depreciation. Contrarily, foreign currency sales mean D_0 takes the value of negative unity and causes a domestic currency appreciation. Therefore, the α_1 sign should intuitively capture this negative relationship across all currency pairs.

This then raises the question as to why this is not the case with the USDMXN exchange rate. One possible explanation for this could be due to the sterilised nature of the intervention; BIS (2013) found that through 2003 to 2010, every instance of intervention was sterilised. They note “the results of each intervention auction are notified to the office that plans the daily liquidity requirements in the money market. This office then takes into account the auction’s results, in effect, sterilising the intervention”. As stated previously, the currency impact of sterilised intervention is predominantly restricted to the signalling channel, as the portfolio-balance channel’s influence is marginal other than in specific macroeconomic conditions. Since consistent and regular foreign currency sales provides limited new information over the direction of future monetary policy to market participants, one might argue that purely sterilized intervention with minimal signalling effects could lead to ineffective central bank intervention. This is supported by the findings of Quintanilla et al (2011) who stated that for the MXN, “total interventions had no significant effect through the signalling channel”. Notably, the other three currencies utilise a combination of sterilised and non-sterilised intervention, which provides

more avenues for the signalling and money supply channels to take effect, perhaps leading to the difference in statistical significance.

Variance estimation diagnostic tests

The Lagrange Multiplier test for ARCH effects provides evidence for the presence of ARCH effects across all considered currencies pairs. More specifically, the p-values for the first four lags across each currency is equal to 0.00, showing the χ^2 statistic is statistically significant at the stringent $\alpha = 1\%$ significance level. This means there is sufficient evidence to accept the alternative hypothesis H_1 : there are ARCH effects. Therefore, an ARCH-type model is an appropriate specification for modelling conditional variances.

Furthermore, the stationarity of ARCH effects can be tested using the “stationarity condition”. In ARCH modelling, a necessary condition for stationarity is that the sum of the ARCH and GARCH parameters (i.e. $\beta_1 + \delta_1$) must be less than one. Stationarity of ARCH effects is important as it ensures the conditional variance of the process remains finite and do not explode over time. Across the four baseline models, the summed ARCH and GARCH terms are less than unity in the case of USDJPY and USDTRY. For the other two, since the summed parameters only exceed unity marginally, the regression results are still considered “marginally stable”, however over longer forecast periods, the model may exhibit slowly explosive behaviours. A marginally stable regression is also more forgiving in a Threshold GARCH model, as the model inherently captures asymmetric effects.

The squared standardized residuals of the GARCH(1,1) model also reveals an absence of significant autocorrelation across all four currencies, which Bollerslev and Mikkelsen (1996) argue that the model has captured all the ARCH effects.

The residuals are also tested for normality. Using the Skewness and Kurtosis for Normality test in Stata, there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis H_0 : residuals are normally distributed. This is the case with all 4 currencies, which returns p-values of 0.00 for both skewness and kurtosis; none of the currencies display Gaussian residuals. The kurtosis and skew of the residuals are summarised below:

Currency	Mean	Variance	Kurtosis	Skew
AUD	0.000018	0.0072137	14.46632	-0.3221572
JPY	0.0000696	0.0065379	8.392586	0.3446721
TRY	-0.0003506	0.0102892	49.5237	0.15099
MXN	0.0000105	0.0000614	9.285876	-0.6355267

In the case of the Threshold GARCH model, the skewness of the errors provides greater evidence for the existence of volatility asymmetry. For the case of a negative (positive) skew, significant negative (positive) shocks tend to lead to further increases in conditional variances, whilst the same cannot be said for large positive (negative) shocks.

Note that the heteroskedasticity of errors in the mean-estimation equation are not tested. This is because the Threshold GARCH, along with any ARCH-type specification, treats the heteroskedasticity of errors as a variance to be modelled.

Variance estimation characteristics – Baseline

Consider the baseline model, which attempts to capture whether asymmetric volatility is present. The γ_1 coefficient on the threshold term captures the extent to which a negative shock will affect the conditional variances compared to a positive shock. From an econometric view, when a significant negative shock occurs, the daily returns are overestimated by the mean estimation, meaning there is greater exogenous variability in the dependent variable that is absorbed by the error term. This means in the case of a negative shock, the error term is likely to be de-triggered (through the D_1 dummy), and the impact of a shock on conditional variance is given by β_1 . Likewise, a positive shock is likely to trigger the threshold γ_1 coefficient, causing the combined impact of a shock to be $\beta_1 + \gamma_1$. Notably, γ_1 is statistically significant at the $\alpha = 1\%$ level for all currency pairs other than USDTRY. This means that out of the four currencies considered, AUD, JPY and MXN showed VA, whilst TRY did not.

In the case of the Turkish Lira, the absence of VA contradicts previous literature. Killiç (2010), using Fractionally Integrated GARCH models, stated “we find statistically significant asymmetry and peakedness in... time-varying volatility with long-range dependence in conditional volatility”. Indeed, Fractionally Integrated GARCH models are able to capture the long-memory volatility effects (higher order correlation structures), which the Threshold GARCH model omits. This is particularly relevant for the USDTRY exchange rate, as Akgul and Sayyan (2008) found that “Long memory or integrated GARCH models outperforms stable GARCH models for the USD/TRY and CAD/TRY while short memory GARCH models outperforms long-memory GARCH models for other exchange rates”. This supports the findings of Arachchi (2018) discussed previously, whereby the optimal Asymmetric GARCH model to capture volatility asymmetry is dependent on the specific currency pair. Notably, Alptekin (2007) also finds evidence for long-memory volatility effects for the USDTRY

exchange rate, though expressed the difficulties in explaining the stochastic processes that may cause such a phenomenon.

Among the currencies where VA was identified, an interesting dichotomy emerges; AUD and MXN have negative γ_1 coefficients, whilst JPY has a positive γ_1 coefficient. This means, for AUD and MXN, a negative shock that de-triggers the threshold term faces a higher conditional variance and thus volatility relative to a positive shock. This is captured by the combined $\beta_1 + \gamma_1$ shock coefficient that is higher during a negative shock (as the negative γ_1 is de-triggered), and represents the traditional direction of VA. Meanwhile for the JPY, a negative shock that de-triggers the threshold term decreases the combined $\beta_1 + \gamma_1$ shock coefficient due to the positive γ_1 coefficient, implying a lower volatility response. This represents the opposite direction of VA, as it is positive shocks to the exchange rate that causes greater volatility relative to negative shocks. This provides supporting evidence for the findings of Cho (2022) who found safe haven currencies, like Japan, have an inverted relationship to volatility asymmetry compared to risk-on currencies. Whilst she suggests this caused by the positive relationship between currency valuations and volatility, the theoretical framework outlined in this dissertation also provides a possible explanation.

Namely, the idiosyncratic response functions of differing central banks alongside the unique economic challenges that a currency might face may cause the split direction of asymmetry. For example, the Japanese Ministry of Finance has a heavy bias towards foreign currency purchases given its ancillary mandate to prevent excessive upward exchange rate pressure. Japan has faced a unique economic challenge since the Lost Decade, buffeted by near-zero inflation and low growth. Thus, a persistently strong yen would compound these existing problems through reduced imported inflation and less competitive exports, harming its Balance of Payments and therefore growth. This means that following a positive shock that induces significant and sustained yen appreciation, the Ministry of Finance may see greater incentive to intervene compared to a significant negative shock. Because the intervention is more frequent during positive shocks, it is these periods that experience greater volatility through the intervention-created disorderly buy/sell signals. Meanwhile, the significant negative skew of USD and MXN intervention (see Figure 7) suggests a bias towards large foreign exchange sales to prevent excessive depreciation. Therefore, for these currencies, it is following negative shocks that the central bank is more likely to intervene and a create volatility response.

This provides evidence for the importance of the relative frequencies of foreign currency purchases versus sales in causing the observed asymmetric volatility. For risk-on currencies such as AUD and MXN, because the central bank is intervening more frequently following negative shocks relative to positive shocks, it is these periods that will see the greater volatility

responses caused by intervention. For safe havens such as the JPY, as the central bank intervenes more during positive shock periods, these periods will observe greater volatility compared to negative shock periods.

Variance estimation characteristics – Sales and Purchases Dummies

For greater insight, the adjusted models with Sales and Purchases Dummies are considered. In the Sales Dummy model, all three currencies that displayed VA have statistically significant γ_2 coefficients at the $\alpha = 1\%$ significance level. This implies that central bank sales of foreign currency have a significant effect on the conditional variance and therefore volatility, since all γ_2 coefficients are positive. This provides strong evidence for the hypothesis that central bank intervention creates higher volatility periods, perhaps through causing heterogeneous exchange rate expectations and disorderly buy/sell signals.

However, the respective coefficient under the Purchase Dummy model, γ_3 , is not significant for the AUD, even at the $\alpha = 10\%$ significance level. For the MXN, γ_3 is not applicable, due to the absence of foreign currency purchases implemented by the Banco de México. Meanwhile for JPY, whilst both γ_2 and γ_3 are both statistically significant, there is a notable disparity in the size of the coefficients.

This further provides support for the hypothesis, whereby sales and purchases have different volatility impacts; it is not just the differing frequencies of intervention that cause VA. Consider first the risk-on currencies AUD and MXN; the asymmetry of impact is evident for both these currencies as only the foreign currency sales that has an impact on conditional variances. One possible reason for why foreign currency purchases do not significantly impact the conditional variance for the AUD is through the significance of the signalling channel. Evidently, market participants react to the sales of foreign currency in a manner which is not found for purchases, implying a difference in the signals that each category of intervention sends to the market. Foreign Currency sales often signal greater economic turmoil beyond what is observed in the currency markets. Consider the 1992-3 period of the Australian economy, which saw the most significant and frequent sales of foreign currency over the past 40 years. With sluggish recovery and rising unemployment, the Australian economy faced an inauspicious outlook. Thus when the central bank intervened with significant foreign currency sales, it may have reinforced the negative economic outlook and added further confusion over the future direction of the exchange rate. This is supported by the findings of Moore (2017) who found that economic uncertainty in Australia is heightened during recessions, elections and policy surprises. This then suggests that during significant downturn periods, uncertainty is pre-heightened and central bank sales exacerbates this effect. As the direction of economic recovery becomes more ambiguous, exchange rate expectations become more heterogeneous, causing greater volatility. Meanwhile,

foreign currency purchases imply significant demand for the risk-on currency which implies lower risk and volatility.

For the JPY model, the γ_2 is noticeably larger than the γ_3 coefficient, implying that foreign currency sales have a greater volatility impact compared to purchases. One might suggest that this goes against intuition, given that it is positive shocks (and thus foreign currency purchases) that cause the observed volatility asymmetry. However, the above logic can also be applied to the JPY, whereby the negative shock causes impacts beyond the foreign exchange market. Thus, whilst strong yen appreciation might cause further economic damage, a large downturn might signify significant existing damage to the macroeconomic environment. However, in order to reconcile the results in the baseline model with the Sales Dummy and Purchase Dummy models, it must be the combination of frequency and impact that derive the level of VA. This is because the positive γ_1 coefficient implies that positive shocks cause VA, yet the foreign currency purchases associated with yen overvaluation has a lower γ_3 coefficient value compared to for that of sales, γ_2 . This means it must be because foreign currency purchases are occurring at a greater frequency that the observed volatility behaviour occurs. This supports the crux of the hypothesis; it is a combination of asymmetric implementation and asymmetric volatility impact that combines to create the overall volatility asymmetry effect.

Another point of interest is that, as previously mentioned, all MXN sales of foreign currency were sterilised. Despite this, government intervention (specifically foreign currency sales) still has a statistically significant impact on conditional variances, and thus volatility. This provides evidence for the importance of the signalling channel in the causation of volatility asymmetry; since there is no net effect on the money supply from intervention, mechanical changes in the direction of key macroeconomic variables cannot be the cause of VA in the case of sterilised intervention. Since previous literature points to the limited validity of the portfolio-balance channel in most macroeconomic settings, signalling must then play a role in the causation of VA. Intuitively, when investors are signalled that the direction of the exchange rate is changing, but the extent is unknown, conflicting expectations over long-run nominal exchange rate values are likely to cause a volatility response.

regression results for the mean and variance estimations

estimation: $R_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 D_{0,t} + \alpha_2 R_{t-1} + \epsilon_t; \epsilon_t \sim N(0, h_t)$

baseline Model: $h_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \delta_1 h_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{1,t-1}$

Model: $h_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 + \delta_1 h_{t-1} + \gamma_1 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{1,t-1} + \gamma_j \epsilon_{t-1} D_{j,t-1}$

	α_1	β_1	δ_1	γ_1	γ_j	
USDAD	BASELINE MODEL	-0.0037869*** (0.0003322)	0.2299427*** (0.0117752)	0.8070606*** (0.0070456)	-0.0820755*** (0.0141845)	---
	WITH SALES DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 2$)	-0.0037869*** (0.0003322)	0.2246367*** (0.0148101)	0.7620713*** (0.032947)	-0.00714881*** (0.0144304)	2.856408*** (0.7660016)
	WITH PURCHASE DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 3$)	-0.0037869*** (0.0003322)	0.2325116*** (0.118429)	0.8058721*** (0.121489)	-0.0818262*** (0.0135184)	10.78057 (6677.373)
USDPY	BASELINE MODEL	-0.0007991*** (0.0003534)	0.1315931*** (0.0112218)	0.7502224*** (0.0405576)	0.1172551*** (0.015566)	---
	WITH SALES DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 2$)	-0.0007991*** (0.0003534)	0.1311269*** (0.0162291)	0.7060878*** (0.0396125)	0.1258857 (0.0162291)	2.258376*** (0.364997)
	WITH PURCHASE DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 3$)	-0.0007991*** (0.0003534)	0.1435199*** (0.012399)	0.7421262*** (0.0366119)	0.1160994 (0.0163839)	1.1312335*** (0.01620157)
USDTRY	BASELINE MODEL	-0.0025302*** (0.0018084)	0.41723*** (0.0225444)	0.5078406*** (0.0207748)	-0.0353484 (0.0220421)	---
	WITH SALES DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 2$)	-0.0025302*** (0.0018084)	0.4194873*** (0.0224993)	0.4970384*** (0.0205373)	-0.0320498 (0.0220477)	3.056433*** (0.312184)
	WITH PURCHASE DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 3$)	-0.0025302*** (0.0018084)	0.4204783*** (0.0227297)	0.5016607*** (0.207424)	-0.0348614 (0.0221553)	-687.1029*** (1.439881)
USDMXN	BASELINE MODEL	0.0000465 (0.0167997)	0.2516123*** (0.256814)	0.897581*** (0.0677687)	-0.0989465*** (0.024017)	---
	WITH SALES DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 2$)	0.0000465 (0.0167997)	0.2828481*** (0.0242934)	0.7798996*** (0.112982)	-0.1212621*** (0.0259448)	9.074161*** (0.2919731)
	WITH PURCHASE DUMMY VARIABLE ($j = 3$)	0.0000465 (0.0167997)	0.2516123*** (0.0256814)	0.897581*** (0.0677687)	-0.0989465*** (0.0256814)	---

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Conclusions and Policy Implications

This dissertation has set out to identify whether central bank intervention in currency markets has a causal effect on volatility asymmetry, whilst building on existing literature by considering the potential intervention channels through which VA might arise, as well as by evaluating a wider spectrum of currency pairs. To this end, three variations of the Threshold GARCH model were utilised; a baseline model aiming to capture whether VA effects are present, and two adjusted models attempting to capture the impact of intervention on conditional variances. The baseline model was able to identify VA in three out of the four models, though missed its existence for USDTRY, potentially given the prevalence of long-memory volatility effects which requires more advanced models such as the FIGARCH specification in order to capture. With the adjusted models, central bank intervention was shown to have a statistically significant impact in causing VA, particularly with foreign currency sales, whilst also displaying asymmetry in the relative impact of sales versus purchases. An important conclusion is the importance of considering both intervention impact and intervention frequency in order to reconcile the 3 model specifications and to obtain the overall VA effect.

Furthermore, the comparison of sterilised versus non-sterilised intervention provided insight into the intervention channels that may cause volatility asymmetry. VA was observed in the USDMXN exchange despite the use of sterilised intervention and no statistically significant impact of intervention on the mean estimation. This shows the importance of the signalling channel in the creation of VA, given the restricted direct impact that sterilised intervention has on currency supply and demand dynamics.

The modelling has not been without its limitations and drawbacks, however. Firstly, a key improvement would be evaluating a wider range of currency pairs in order to identify trends more explicitly across different classes of currency. However, as many central banks refrain from disclosing their intervention data, the scope of this research was greatly limited. Furthermore, access to intra-day trading data would enable the use of more sophisticated econometric techniques that can capture the more nuanced aspects of volatility behaviours, for example FIGARCH models to identify long-memory volatility effects. An improvement over the implemented econometric method could be to introduce an additional model specification which includes a dummy, capturing whether intervention was sterilised or not. This would then allow for greater insight into the relative effects of different intervention channels i.e. monetary supply channels versus signalling. Notably, however, creating such a dataset would have its own challenges, given that sterilisation is a spectrum and highly time dependent.

This study also provides some practical implications for policymaking. If the aim of a central bank is to temper exchange rate volatility, ensuring credible and consistent monetary policy implementation is essential. This creates an environment whereby the directions of future policy decisions, macroeconomic variables and ultimately the exchange rate are not subject to unnecessary uncertainty. This also highlights the importance of reliable forward guidance; a central bank backtracking on a previously stated policy/outlook ultimately heightens uncertainty across financial markets as market participants adjust their expectations and strategies accordingly.

Furthermore, understanding that that foreign currency sales exacerbates volatility more than purchases is important for central banks. If the purpose of intervention is to introduce liquidity into the foreign exchange market to temper volatile price movements, forms of liquidity injection other than foreign currency sales should be considered in order to avoid the heightened volatility response.

Appendix – regression implementation in Stata

Stata was used to run the regression, given that it has a Threshold GARCH package that can be used. The following code is what was used for the USDAUD regression.

```
25 . gen ndate = date(date, "DMY")
26
27 . tsset ndate
28
29 Time variable: ndate, 10595 to 22826, but with gaps
30     Delta: 1 unit
31
32 . gen rusdaud_lagged = rusdaud[_n-1]
33 (1 missing value generated)
```

This section of code adjusts the formatting of the data such that it can be utilised in a time-series regression. A new variable is created *rusdaud_lagged*, denoting the USDAUD currency returns lagged by one day.

```
36 . regress rusdaud iusdaud rusdaud_lagged
37
53 . estat archlm, lags(1/4)
54
```

Here, the mean-estimation regression is run. The *susdaud_lagged* component represents R_{t-1} and *iusdaud* represents $D_{0,t}$. Using this initial regression, the LM test can then be run with the code:

Which will return statistics following a χ^2 distribution with the null hypothesis H_0 : there are no ARCH effects and the alternative hypothesis H_1 : there is an ARCH(p) disturbance.

Once the LM test confirms the existence of ARCH effects, the Threshold GARCH model can be run, using the code:

```
68 . arch rusdaud iusdaud rusdaud_lagged, arch(1) garch(1) tarch(1)
```

This runs the GTARCH regression, with the first three variables after “*arch*” capturing the mean regression and the latter 3 capturing various ARCH effects. *arch*(1) captures the lagged squared-residual ϵ_{t-1}^2 component. *garch*(1) captures the lagged conditional variance term h_{t-1} . *tarch*(1) captures the response mechanism that is triggered when errors cross the zero boundary (through a dummy variable), and it is through this term where the effects of volatility asymmetry are captured. This baseline code can then be applied to the other three currency pairs, and then their outputs can be compared.

To capture the impact that central bank intervention has on volatility asymmetry, an additional dummy term is added to the TGARCH regression. The *het(sales_dummy)* captures the $\gamma_2 \epsilon_{t-1}^2 D_{j,t-1}$ term in the case of a sale ($j = 2$) and *het(purchase_dummy)* reflects this term in the case of a purchase ($j = 3$), that is, in each case the interaction between the lagged squared errors and lagged dummy value is included in the model.

```
266
267 . arch rusdaud iusdaud rusdaud_lagged, het(sales_dummy) arch(1) garch(1) tarch(1)
348
349 . arch rusdaud iusdaud rusdaud_lagged, het(purchase_dummy) arch(1) garch(1) tarch(1)
```

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